

Removal of fluoride by bentonite minerals of Rajmahal Hills

A. K. Jha^a and B. Mishra^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, G. B. College, Naugachia-853 204, Bihar, India

E-mail : ashokjha39@gmail.com

^bFormerly P.G. Department of Chemistry, T. M. Bhagalpur University, Bhagalpur-812 007, Bihar, India

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Abstract : Fluoride present beyond the permissible limit causes dental or skeletal fluorosis. The main source of fluoride in natural water are fluorite, fluorapatite and cryolites. The task of providing fluoride free water to the villages using low cost technology is important. In the present work bentonite minerals of Rajmahal Hills at different places have been collected and adsorption characteristics was evaluated with different doses of mineral. The kinetics of adsorption has also been studied. Though useful practices of adsorption by low grade coal, brick powder, lime and alum are present, bentonite mineral of Rajmahal Hills has been found to be good low cost adsorbent for defluoridation. The results show that it holds good potential for removal of fluoride.

Keywords : Adsorbent, bentonite, fluorosis.

Introduction

Millions of people in India is facing the problem of fluorosis. Fluorine is present in a component of rocks and minerals. India is considered to be one of the important country having fluoride bearing minerals. In the acid medium F could be associated with silica in six or four co-ordinated structure. According to Hem (1992) AlF complexes are likely to be found in water, whose pH is below neutrality.

Natural concentration of fluoride in groundwater depends on the availability of fluorine in the rock. Water encounters the minerals e.g. fluorite and fluorapatite in its flow path. Besides this fluorides used in insecticides, disinfectants and preservatives are also potential source of fluorine in groundwater. Phosphatic fertilizer contains nearly 1–3% of fluoride. This enriches the soils and percolates to the ground water. India is also among the worst affected countries. Its millions of people are affected by endemic fluorosis^{1–3}. So the objective of providing fluoride free water is the application of ecofriendly low cost technology. Some useful practices are adsorption on activated carbon, ion exchange by zeolites, silica gel, sodium aluminate, use of bauxite, lime and alum. The activated alumina has produced good results in defluoridation^{4–7}. Thus the precipitation and adsorption

methods are most preferred. Coconut shell carbon has also been used for defluoridations. Some cheap and ecofriendly methods e.g. use of bioadsorbents like sawdust and cowdung have also been tried^{9,10}.

Though Nalgonda technique of defluoridation is efficient and cost effective, it converts a large portion of ionic fluoride (67–87%) into soluble aluminium complex and removes only a small portion of fluoride in the form of precipitate (18–33%). Residual aluminium is also dangerous to human health as aluminium is a neurotoxin and has been reported to cause Alzheimer's disease¹¹. Bentonite is also one of the natural adsorbent for removal of fluoride¹². So the bentonite minerals of Rajmahal Hills have been tried for defluoridation of drinking water.

These bentonites locally available in the range of Rajmahal Hills are nontoxic and low cost adsorbent. Bentonite is an absorbent aluminium phyllosilicate consisting mostly of montmorillonite^{13–15}.

Results and discussion

Adsorption is the phenomenon whereby molecules adhere to a surface when they come into contact. The extent of removal of fluoride by adsorption depends on the diffusion of the particle to the external surface of the mineral.

The effect of adsorption dosage on adsorption of fluoride was studied for bentonite minerals for 1 h. The results presented the adsorption of fluoride vs adsorbent dose in Fig. 1. The bentonite minerals adsorbed the fluoride below permissible limit.

Fig. 1. Concentration of fluoride ion after treatment with different dose of bentonite minerals.

The adsorption of fluoride was studied at different contact time with a dose of 1 g/100 ml. The kinetics was studied at 60 min, 75 min, 90 min and 120 min. Fluoride adsorption was studied at different time intervals shown by Fig. 2. It is observed that with the increase in contact time, the fluoride removal increased. F^- concentration decreased almost linearly with time within the experimental range of 2 h.

Straight line is obtained when $\log(a - x)$ vs t is plotted for different samples of bentonites in Fig. 3. The linear plots indicate the applicability of first order kinetics equation.

Thus in the present work a new adsorbent bentonite mineral was studied for removal of fluoride from synthetic samples. It was found that with increase in contact time, fluoride removal increased. It was concluded that

Fig. 2. Effect of contact time on fluoride removal after a dose of 1 g/100 ml.

Fig. 3. $\log(a - x)$ vs time for different samples of Rajmahal bentonites.

locally available huge reserve of bentonite of Rajmahal Hills of Jharkhand state can be useful for defluoridation.

Experimental

The bentonite samples collected from Rajmahal Hills were tested for montmorillonite by benzidine solution¹⁶. The percentage composition of bentonites has been determined by standard methods^{17,18}. It was then finely pow-

Table 1. Percent analysis data of constituents of Rajmahal bentonites

Code no.	SiO ₂	K ₂ O	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	TiO ₂	MnO ₂	Na ₂ O	MgO	CaO
RB-2	35.60	0.38	32.94	4.10	1.34	0.19	1.34	2.68	6.32
RB-4	42.40	5.45	27.00	4.00	1.40	0.44	3.46	1.26	1.22
RB-5	34.25	1.24	28.30	6.80	2.35	0.14	0.78	4.71	5.66
RB-8	38.10	2.60	34.01	5.00	0.92	0.11	6.58	0.52	1.40
RB-12	47.52	0.34	26.90	2.20	2.15	0	1.48	2.30	2.77

Table 2. Concentration of fluoride ion after treatment with bentonite minerals

Bentonite sample no.	F ⁻ ppm initial	F ⁻ ppm after treatment			
		0.5 g/ 100 ml	1.0 g/ 100 ml	1.2 g/ 100 ml	2.0 g/ 100 ml
RB-2	3.00	2.80	2.38	1.80	0.60
RB-4	3.00	2.90	2.62	2.30	1.20
RB-5	3.00	2.89	2.60	2.32	1.18
RB-8	3.00	2.70	2.40	1.75	0.50
RB-12	3.00	2.90	2.62	2.30	1.18

Different dose of bentonite for a contact time of 60 min.

Table 3. Concentration of fluoride ion after treatment with bentonite mineral

Bentonite Sample no.	F ⁻ ppm initial	F ⁻ ppm after treatment			
		60 min	75 min	90 min	120 min
RB-2	3.00	2.38	1.50	0.90	0.40
RB-4	3.00	2.62	1.75	1.20	0.68
RB-5	3.00	2.60	1.73	1.20	0.65
RB-8	3.00	2.40	1.45	0.86	0.38
RB-12	3.00	2.62	1.75	1.20	0.68

Effect of contact time on fluoride removal after a dose of 1 g/100 ml.

dered to 300 µm size by mesh sieve available in the laboratory and dried in the oven for 1 h. The stock solution of 100 mg/L sodium fluoride was prepared in distilled water and finally 3 mg/L strength of fluoride was prepared by dilution. The bentonite sample was taken in the solution and shaken by mechanical shaker. The solution was filtered by Whatmann filter paper no. 42. The remaining concentration of fluoride was known by ion selective electrode method.

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